

An Analysis of Educators and Teaching Staffs Perceptions of the Kampus Mengajar Program at SDN 9 Batu

Isra Mirat^{1*}, Nadirah², Sam Hermasnyah³

Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidenreng Rappang

Corresponding Author: Isra Mirat isramiratcantik@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to analyze teacher's perceptions through Kampus Mengajar. This research was conducted at SDN 9 Batu, Pitu Riase where the principal, operator and teachers were the respondents. The data collection methods used in this study were interviews and documentation. The data collection methods used in this research are interview and documentation methods. This research used qualitative research method. The results of the research show that the teachers' perceptions of Kampus Mengajar not only provides classroom teaching experience for students, but also help teachers educate and guide students to give better knowledge especially in remote villages and benefits from Kampus Mengajar is very big because there are changes and student progress in learning. Then there is a high motivation that students have to continue learning, increase their knowledge after Kampus Mengajar activities are finished.

INTRODUCTION

Education is something that is very important for human life, because without education humans will be left behind by the times, and education also greatly affects the quality of one's life. Especially now that technological developments are happening so fast, that it forces us all to be able to keep up with the times if we don't want to be left behind. The implementation of education in Indonesia is known as the national education system which is implemented through three educational channels, namely formal education, non-formal education and informal education. The existence of the Covid-19 virus has greatly impacted the educational process which is then shifted to online and offline. This results in a lack of interaction between educators and students directly or face to face at school. Various efforts have been made by both the government and the people of Indonesia to break the Covid-19 chain. By still complying with health protocols and having a conscious attitude of rights and obligations. And also one of them is the policy of implementing Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) and Physical Distancing and Social Distancing by the government which is then recommended to stay at home. This condition inspires all members of the academic community and policy makers in terms of education to pay attention to Indonesian education.

As one of the efforts to improve the educational problems that occur, the Ministry of Education and Culture launched an independent learning program. Merdeka Learning is a policy program from the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia which was designed by the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia for the Advanced Indonesia Cabinet, Nadiem Anwar Makarim. Iwinsah in Winda Anjelani (2021) explains that Freedom of learning is a policy made to provide freedom of reasoning. The importance of freedom in reasoning should be owned by educators first. If it has not been realized in educators, of course it will not be applied to students (Iwinsah, 2020).

Kompasiana (2020) stated, if the independence of learning is fulfilled properly, it will create "free learning" activities and schools are also called independent schools. It is hoped that the independence of learning that is given can improve the quality of education in the school. The creation of this independent learning program was made because of the results of the 2019 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) research. From this research, it can be seen that the results of the assessment of Indonesian students are in a low position. Seeing this fact, Nadiem Makarim created a policy of independent learning.

This policy was made in order to improve the quality of education in Indonesia which is still said to be low. Improving the quality of education is carried out so that Indonesian citizens can follow the development of globalization and can also compete with several developed countries. If the quality of education is not improved, Indonesia will continue to lag behind other countries. Given that this should not happen, the Indonesian government is trying to make several policies that can improve the quality of education. One of the latest policies in Indonesia today is the independent learning policy.

Nadiem Makarim's independent learning program has four main topics, namely: (1) the abolition of the National Examination in schools, (2) the implementation of the USBN which is carried out by each school, (3) simplifying the format of the lesson plan (RPP) for teacher, (4) making the zoning system for new student admissions (PSB) more flexible.

The Kampus Merdeka Program that has been running is a three-semester study program outside the study program. This program is carried out to improve the competence of graduates, both soft skills and hard skills, so that they are more prepared and relevant to the needs of the times and produce graduates with superior and personality traits.

The following Kampus Merdeka programs are currently running: Internships, Independent Studies, Bangkit Program, Indonesia International Student Mobility Awards, Kampus mengajar, Independent Studies - Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, Village Development (KKN Thematic), Independent Campus Young Fighters, Independent Student Exchange, Humanitarian Projects, Research or Research, Entrepreneur.

One of the independent learning programs is the Kampus Merdeka, the Class 1 Kampus Mengajar program in 2020/2021. The Kampus Mengajar program is based on Indonesia's need for student assistance to help teachers and elementary school students to get optimal learning opportunities in limited and critical conditions during the pandemic.

The Kampus Mengajar is a program belonging to the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology. The Kampus Mengajar is part of the Kampus Merdeka which invites all lecturers and students at universities in Indonesia to take a role in responding to educational problems affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, especially in C-accredited elementary schools in the 3T (Tertinggal, Terluar, and Terdepan) areas. In the Kampus Mengajar Program Batch 1, students will be placed in elementary schools throughout Indonesia and assist the teaching and learning process at these schools. For school placements, the intended schools are schools with accreditation C and for schools that are remote or in dire need. For the materials that students participating in the Kampus Mengajar must prepare, among others, Elementary School Pedagogy.

Kampus Mengajar 2021 is a follow-up program from the Pioneer Kampus Mengajar Program which was implemented in 2020 as proof of the campus' dedication through students to move towards the success of national education in a pandemic. Kampus Mengajar with the support of LPDP, the Ministry of Education and Culture launched the Kampus Mengajar program in Schools. MBKM provides the right to study for one semester outside the study program to improve competencies, both soft skills and hard skills so that they can be more prepared and relevant to the needs of the times as future leaders of the nation with superior and personality. Indonesia is in need of assistance from various parties to move synergistically to succeed in national education. This movement can be done by anyone including students to help school.

For the past eighteen years, Indonesia has been ranked at the bottom for literacy and numeracy scores and the pandemic has made it more challenging for Indonesia's PR to catch up. Indonesia needs students to become teachers' partners in developing interesting literacy and numeracy learning. This opportunity will hone students' social skills and character, especially creativity, leadership, and other interpersonal skills through this experience.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Kampus Mengajar policy made by the Ministry of Education and Culture aims to plan university alumni with good quality, excellence, critical of the needs of the times, and ready to become leaders in the future with the spirit of nationalism. Through this program, students are given the freedom to conduct lectures outside their study program, and to practice directly in the community. This is intended to strengthen students and adapt to the style or abilities of each student. Conceptually, Kampus Mengajar policies are considered very significant with the world of work, in accordance with competency-based curriculum and character education (Priatmoko and Dzakiyyah 2020).

The results of the study of other literature also prove that Kampus Mengajar can inspire many things, especially in university policies that aim to provide opportunities for universities so that they can produce more qualified alumni. (Amalia Mia 2021) Regardless of the pros and cons of opinions about Kampus Mengajar policies, the policy view is actually very supportive of the continuity between what they get in theory with what is in the classroom during college, with the reality encountered in the workplace. Therefore, students are asked to become the best alumni who are able to understand theoretical concepts conceptually but also must be able to implement the knowledge gained in the facts of everyday life. Therefore, The Kampus Mengajar policy is one of the right resolutions to reduce the unemployment rate in Indonesia. (Apshaha Eia Nagita & Farid Setiawan 2022).

The learning process in the concept of Kampus Mengajar is one form of implementing student-focused learning. On the one hand, Kampus Mengajar policies face many challenges but also provide opportunities for students to hone their abilities, skills, integrity, independence, and understand various scientific aspects that become students' capital and equipment in the future in facing employment. The Kampus Mengajar policy is implied so that students are prepared from the start with employment opportunities (Suryaman 2020).

Because researcher want to know the opinions of teachers at SDN 9 BATU as one of the schools where the Kampus Mengajar is implemented because researchers have not found previous research that discusses teacher perceptions about the Kampus Mengajar, so the researcher is interested in doing this research.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Qualitative research is research conducted with certain settings that exist in real life (natural) with the aim of investigating and understanding

phenomena: what happened, why did it happen, and how did it happen? Qualitative research aims to gain a deep understanding of human and social problems, not to describe the surface of a reality as quantitative research with positivism does. Because the researcher interprets how the subject gets meaning from the surrounding environment, and how that meaning affects their behavior. The research was conducted in a natural setting, not the result of treatment or manipulation of the variables involved.

The purpose of qualitative research can be seen from: (1) Depicting the object of research (describing object), so that the object of research can be interpreted, it needs to be described by means of photographing, video, illustrating and narrating. This depiction can be done on objects in the form of events, social interactions, religious social activities, and so on. (2) Expressing the meaning behind the phenomena (exploring meaning behind the phenomena), the meaning behind the phenomenon/fact can be revealed if the researcher shows and reveals it through in-depth interviews (dept interview) and participating observations (participation observation). (3) Explaining the phenomenon that occurs (explaining object), phenomena that appear in the field are sometimes not the same as what is the goal (Setiawan & Anggito, 2006).

Data Source Research

Data sources are the places where the data to be studied. One type of research data source is respondents who are also the source of data in this research. The respondents in this were principals, teacher and school operator at SDN 9 Batu.

Techniques of Collecting Data

The research instrument is the method used to obtain the required data or information. Research instruments are scientifically designed and systematic tools used to collect, measure, and analyze data related to research interests and alignment. The research instruments used by researchers are interviews, and documentation. Interview An interview is seen as a verbal conversation between two people with the aim of gathering relevant information for research purposes. Information or data is collected from interview. The form of interview used by the researcher is a semi- structured interview. This type of interview is more independent than the structured interview. The purpose of this interview is to find problems more openly, where the parties invited to the interview are asked for their opinions and ideas. Documentation is a complementary source in a study. Some of the facts and information also come from materials in the form of documentaries. In this study, researchers collect information through documentation which can be in the form of photos, writings, videos, audio or recordings and documents related to this research.

Techniques of Data Analysis

Noeng Muhadjir (1998) in Rijali (2018) Defines data analysis as an effort to systematically search and organize notes from observations, interviews, and others to increase the researcher's understanding of the case being studied and

present it as a finding for others. Meanwhile, to improve this understanding, the analysis needs to be continued by trying to find meaning.”

In this study, researchers used data analysis techniques qualitative. Qualitative data analysis is the interpretation of the concept of all existing data using analytical strategies that aim to change or translate raw data into a description or description and explanation of the phenomenon being researched and studied. (Junaid, 2016).

(In Sugiono, 2017:369) Miles and Huberman (1984), argue that activities in qualitative data analysis are carried out in an interactive way and take place continuously until complete so that the data is saturated. Activities in data analysis, namely data reduction, data display, and conclusion. The analysis steps are shown as follows: Data Reduction is the process of selecting, focuses on simplifying, abstracting, and transforming rough data that emerges from written records in the field (Rijali, 2018:91). When conducting research, there will be a lot of data collected by researchers, so data reduction is needed to select data, focus on information related to researchteacher's perception of Kampus Mengajar. Thus the data that has been reduced will provide a clearer picture, and make it easier for researchers to collect further data, and look for it when needed. Data display After the data is reduced, the next step is to display the data. Data presentation is an activity when a collection of information is compiled, thus giving the possibility of drawing conclusions and taking action (Rijali, 2018:91). In qualitative research, the most frequently used data presentation is in the form of narrative text. Conclusions drawing and verification Sugiyono in Wandu argues that data verification is an attempt to find, test, re-check or understand the meaning or meaning, regularities, patterns, explanations, plots, causes and effects, or prepositions. While the conclusion can be a description or description of an object that was previously dim or dark so that after research it becomes clear, it can be a causal or interactive relationship, hypothesis or theory (Wandu, Nuharsono, and Raharjo,2013).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study is to find two things in answering the research question. First, teachers' perceptions of the Kampus Mengajar and second, the benefits of the Kampus Mengajar. This research uses two methods, namely interviews and documentation.

The Teacher's Perception of Kampus Mengajar

Teacher perceptions about Kampus Mengajar program shows that this program not only provide classroom teaching experience, but can also help improve the ability to work together between teachers and students they also help us as teachers to educate or guide students to provide better knowledge, especially in remote villages. They is a great need for development, especially in remote schools, so there is a need for outside experience to motivate elementary school children in Lariu hamlet to continue learning and can increase children's knowledge about learning in the classroom. For students, the can apply the knowledge that has been obtained on campus to children in schools, especially

in elementary schools and have a direct positive impact on children as new knowledge that previously there may still have not been taught by their teachers.

The Benefits of Having a Kampus Mengajar

The impact of the Kampus Mengajar is very useful in the development of creative and innovative learning strategies and models in the target education unit, the enthusiasm of the children increases and then there is also a lot of knowledge gained from students both in the teaching process and in outside activities, there are developments, especially in children in elementary schools in Lariu hamlet who used to be always late, after students were here helping to give advice or as pressure on children so that they can now be overcome. Besides that the high motivation that children have again after the outdoor and indoor activities carried out by students who come to lariu hamlet. Opens up space for students to be able to apply their skills and knowledge in helping children in basic education units.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion above regarding the teacher's perception of Kampus Mengajar and the benefits of having a Kampus Mengajar the research concludes as follows:

The teacher's perception of Kampus Mengajar

Kampus Mengajar program not only provide classroom teaching experience, but can also help improve the ability to work together between teachers and students they also help us as teachers to educate or guide as to provide better knowledge, especially in remote villages. For students to apply the knowledge that has been obtained on campus to children in schools, especially in elementary schools and have a direct positive impact on children as new knowledge that previously there may still be something that has not been taught by their teachers.

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This researcher is still far from perfect because there are still some aspects of Kampus mengajar understanding that have not been covered, but the researcher really hopes that this research can be useful for readers so that future researchers can conduct more complex research.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on it "An Analysis Of Educators And Teaching Staffs Perceptions Of The Kampus Mengajar Program At SDN 9 Batu."

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